

models can remove this problem, by reducing the manual labour and accelerating the overall required time to plan it.

B. Elevation Model Analysis

The elevation model used is the DEM3 of the SRTM, an international project led by the United States National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency and the United States National Aeronautics and Space Administration.

Fig. 2. DEM3 Coverage Map.

The DEM3 model is stored on *.hgt* files. The files are named according to the latitude and longitude they represent. For example, the file N33W177 contains the data between latitudes 33N e 34N and between the longitudes 177W e 188W [1].

Fig. 3. Colorized *.hgt* file.

Each DEM3 table contains 1201 rows and 1201 columns. Each cell contains the elevation of a square with an edge of 300ft. The extra row and column represent the right and bottom borders of the area, which is repeated in adjacent files.

The data is stored in the *.hgt* files through signed integer bytes. The bytes are in Motorola big-endian order, which means the most important byte of a couple comes first. Current computers use the little-endian format for reading bytes, which the most important byte comes last. To correctly read the file, it's necessary to perform a byte-swapping operation, converting the bytes to an integer by reading them backwards.

Fig. 4. Extract of file N00W056.hgt

With the resolution of 1201, an *.hgt* file contains 1.442.401 entries of elevation data. Considering each entry contains 2 bytes, each file contains approximately 2.75MB. Considering a complete mapping of the surface of the Earth, there should be about 64.800 *.hgt* files, totaling 174GB of data loaded on memory. However, considering the mapping was only realized on firm land, which represents 29% of the total surface, loading the entire data should require about 50GB of memory.

To process each file, it would take 8.884.802 cycles of the processor, or, using technical terms, $O(2.884.802)$. If the storage was done in an HDD with a reading speed of 150MB/s, it would take about 6 minutes to read the entire dataset. To convert the entire data to readable integers, with a processing speed of 2.9GHz, it would take about 19 seconds.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Initial Calculation

Considering a flight path with straight levelled segments, each segment is represented by two points: a starting point (P_i) and an ending point (P_f). According to the default rules to calculate the MORA, it must consider the elevation in an area delimited by all the points with a distance less or equal to 10NM to the route. To perform the calculations, the area can be represented by a quadrilateral of vertices V_1, V_2, V_3 e V_4 , with edges forming right angles, with the size of the smallest edges of 20NM and with the size of the largest edges equal to the route length. The route segment should be centred in this quadrilateral.

Fig. 5. Search area quadrilateral of the highest elevation per segment.

Having θ as the angle between P_i e P_f , the vertices V_1 , V_2 , V_3 e V_4 are found through sins and cosines of the angles $\theta - 45^\circ$, $\theta + 45^\circ$, $\theta + 135^\circ$, and $\theta - 135^\circ$, respectively, with a length of $20\sqrt{2}NM$.

To avoid processing extra *.hgt* files, boundaries of latitudes and longitudes are calculated, using the minimum *.hgt* files possible to process the quadrilateral set above. These boundaries are represented by a new quadrilateral, aligned with the axis \overline{NS} e \overline{WE} .

To read the *.hgt* files, a buffer size must be chosen. The buffer size is the number of bytes that will be read each time. There isn't an ideal value for every machine, requiring an initial test in each system to verify the ideal size. To get the elevation of each coordinate, two bytes are read each time. After reading, the bytes are inverted and then converted to an integer and stored into a table.

Fig. 6. Search points of the highest elevation

To get the highest elevation of each segment, the search quadrilateral is split into two triangles, and each point in the boundaries area is analysed recursively, checking if it belongs to one of the two triangles set above, and if its elevation is higher than the previous registered point. If it is true, then this point gets registered as the highest point, as well as its elevation. The same is done for the lowest elevations.

B. Final Calculations

With the data of the highest and lowest elevation of each segment, the difference is analysed. If the difference is greater than 1.000ft, the terrain is considered mountainous, and 2.000ft are added to the highest elevation of the segment to get the MORA. If the difference is lesser than 1.000ft, 1.000ft is added to the highest elevation to get the MORA.

IV. RESULTS

To test the system, a program was developed to calculate the MORAs of routes of 1h of flight, with 6 segments of 10 minutes each.

Fig. 7. MORA Calculator Program

The accuracy check was done comparing the results of the program with the MORAs calculated by fighter pilots of the Brazilian Air Force, which were based on visual charts.

TABLE I. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE CALCULATIONS MADE BY HUMANS AND BY A COMPUTER

<i>Planning</i>	<i>Human Calculation Time</i>	<i>Computer Calculation Time</i>	<i>Human Calculation Accuracy</i>	<i>Calculation Time Ratio</i>
1	02min 55s	05s	33%	35:1
2	04min 05s	05s	66%	49:1
3	02min 52s	05s	33%	34:1
4	03min 27s	05s	66%	41:1
5	02min 28s	04s	33%	37:1
Average	03min 09s	05s	50%	37:1

The table above is a comparison between the calculations done by the pilots and the program. The fighter pilots took about 3min and 9 seconds to calculate the MORAs of each assigned route, while the program took approximately 5 seconds to do the same job, which is 37 times faster than the pilots. Also, 50% of the routes planned by the pilots had MORA miscalculations, while the program had zero errors, which either they missed higher elevations in the route, which would result in a higher MORA, or chose elevations which weren't in the 10NM radius, which would make the MORA unnecessarily higher.

The values found by the computer program were later checked and all the elevation peaks found were consistent with the visual charts.

V. CONCLUSION

Each MORA could be calculated based on the available elevation models of Earth, reading the SRTM files through byte-swapping and searching for the highest elevation points of each section of the route.

For mission planning of routes of about 1h of flight, the planning time was reduced in approximately 3 minutes.

Considering the planning phase has other steps not mentioned here, and with the current processing technology of data, it's probable that other steps can be cut down, like the selection of control points, split plans, radar detours and so on. The automation of these processes will one day dismiss pilots from planning their flight navigation, requiring only the insertion of the mission data so the computer can perform all the calculations.

REFERENCES

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